

RehabMove 2018: THE EFFECT OF FORE-AFT CRANK POSITION ON THE BIOMECHANICS, COORDINATION AND PHYSIOLOGY OF RECUMBENT HANDCYCLING.

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Recumbent handcycles are used for different Paralympic sports and recreational competitions. These handcycles aim to benefit the athlete for an optimal athletic performance, yet little research has been done on how to individually configure the handcycle to the athlete. The objective of the current study was to investigate the effect of four different fore-aft crank positions relative to arm length on 1) the resulting elbow and shoulder angles, 2) the consequent propulsion kinematics and kinetics, and 3) the physiological responses.

Twelve able bodied male participants were tested on crank distances standardised at 94%, 97%, 100% and 103% of the participants' arm length, while performing two submaximal exercise tests in a recumbent handcycle attached to an ergometer (Cyclus2, 30 and 60 W, 3min, 70 rpm). The kinematics (Vicon) kinetics (Rotor instrumented crank) and physiological responses (Cortex) were continuously measured. A two-way repeated measures Anova (Fore-aft position and power output) was performed on 1) the resulting elbow angle and shoulder protraction during max extension. 2) the torque (Nm) during different stages of the cycle and the percentage of work done during the pull phase (%). 3) the mechanical efficiency, VO₂ (L/min) HR (beats/min).

The manipulation relative to arm length ranged 5.5 to 8.5 cm between individuals. This resulted in significant kinematic changes in both the elbow flexion-extension and shoulder protraction. Consequently, a shift in the distribution of kinetic work production was observed over the propulsion cycle. Despite these changes in propulsion kinetics there were no significant changes in oxygen consumption. The kinetic variables indicated that a fore-aft position of 94% might have been most favourable, since this configuration resulted in the lowest percentage of work done in the pull phase and led to the most equal distribution of torque.